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SUPPORT INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS IN SCIENCE FOR GRADE 9 LEARNERS

ANICIA S. VELASCO, EdD.

Teacher III

Galvan National High School

Nueva Ecija, Region III

DISSERTATION ABSTRACT

Title: **SUPPORT INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS IN SCIENCE FOR GRADE 9 LEARNERS**

Author: Anicia S. Velasco

Degree: Doctor of Education

Institution: Lyceum-Northwestern University
Institute of Graduate and Professional Studies
Dagupan City

Adviser: Ricky C. Junio, Ed.D.

Abstract:

This study sought to assess the level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students in Galvan High School, Guimba West District, Nueva Ecija during the school year 2020-2021 through the quantitative-descriptive research design. The quantitative-descriptive research design was utilized to determine the level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students based on their final rating for school year 2020-2021. It was also used to look into the least learned competencies in Science of the Grade 9 students. Based on the findings, support instructional materials were proposed to enhance the level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students. The developed support instructional materials were evaluated by experts as to their acceptability in terms of content, quality of presentation, and physical make-up. The sources of data in this study were the teachers of Science in Galvan High School, Guimba West District, Nueva Ecija who provided data needed to answer the sub-problems raised in the study. Summary of Findings: 1.0 Level of Academic Performance in Science of the Grade 9 Students 1.1 There were 14 Grade 9 students or 5.86% who obtained final ratings in Science of 95-100% described as "outstanding" performance. 1.2 There were 24 Grade 9 students or 10.04% who obtained

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final ratings in Science of 90-94% described as "above average" performance. 1.3 Fifty four Grade 9 students or 22.59% obtained final ratings in Science of 85-89% described as "average" performance. 1.4 There were 147 Grade 9 students or 61.51% who obtained final ratings in Science of 80-84% described as "fair" performance. 2.0 Least Learned Competencies in Science The least learned competencies in Science of the Grade 9 students determined based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) are the following: 2.1 Explain how the respiratory and circulatory systems work; 2.2 Describe basic features and importance of photosynthesis; 2.3 Explain how the structure of the carbon atom affects the type of bonds it forms; 2.4 Use the mole concept to express mass of substance; 2.5 Explain what happens when volcanoes erupt; 2.6 Show which constellations may be observed at different times of the year; 2.7 Explain how ions are formed; 2.8 Describe the different types of volcanoes; 2.9 Recognize different types of compounds based on their properties; and 2.10 Describe certain climate phenomena that occur on a global level. 3.0 Support Instructional Materials in Science Support instructional materials in Science for Grade 9 students were proposed to enhance their level of academic performance. 4.0 Acceptability of the Support Instructional Materials in Science 4.1 In terms of content, the support instructional materials are "very acceptable" with average WM of 4.53, with all items as "very acceptable" also with WM of 4.52, 4.50, 4.55, 4.54, and 4.55. 4.2 In terms of quality of presentation, the materials were rated "very acceptable" with average WM of 4.52, with all items as "very acceptable" with WM of 4.51, 4.55 and 4.50. 4.3 In terms of physical make-up, the materials were "very acceptable" with average WM of 4.52, with all items also rated "very acceptable" with WM of 4.55, 4.51, and 4.50. 4.4 The support instructional materials were "very acceptable" with overall WM of 4.52.

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: 1. Most of the Grade 9 students have fair level of academic performance in Science which indicates weak acquisition of skills and concepts in Science. 2. The least learned competencies in Science of the Grade 9 students are explaining how the respiratory and circulatory systems work, describing basic features and importance of photosynthesis, and explaining how the structure of the carbon atom affects the type of bonds it forms. 3. Support instructional materials in Science were proposed for the Grade 9 students to enhance their level of academic performance. 4. The proposed support instructional materials in Science are very acceptable based on the evaluation of experts.

On the basis of the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were offered: 1. The proposed support instructional materials should be considered for use by school authorities concerned to enhance the level of academic performance of Grade 9 students. 2. The developed support instructional materials should be tried out on a bigger scale for further improvement of the materials. 3. Teachers should be encouraged to develop instructional materials particularly on subject/ topics where most students encounter difficulties. 4. The school administration should provide support in the production of instructional materials developed by teachers. 5. Other researchers may conduct similar studies on a wider scope to validate the findings of the study.

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CHAPTER 1 THE PROBLEM

Rationale

The global importance of science and technology which dominates in every society requires an educational system that provides a venue for the development of scientific knowledge and skills. Evidently, the rapid development of this field of knowledge through scientific inventions and discoveries posts a challenge to educational institutions to contribute their part in this growing demand of scientific inquiry.

Science education is concerned with the developing of technologically literate citizens who understand how science, technology, and society influence one another and who are able to use this knowledge in their everyday activities. A study of science is important because it has the potential for improving the quality of life and making the world safer, empowers people, giving them greater control over their lives by providing path ways for finding answers to questions.

Science education is also the field concerned with sharing science content and process. The application of science has transformed the world through dramatic advances in almost all fields including medicine, engineering, electronics, aeronautics etc. and in more recent times dramatic leaps in computer technology have revolutionized in particular the information and communications sector.

Science teaching involves teaching students to use their knowledge, beliefs and metacognitive and effective thought processes to generate new, fruitful, and transferable conceptions that have personal and everyday meaning and significance. As a result, effective science teaching leaves students with the ability and the motivation to solve problems scientifically and to carry out scientific investigation. Hence, effective instructional strategies involve knowledge of multiple methods or activities sequences that lead to successful student learning and a specific concept or process skill (Rogayan and Dollete, 2019).

Students' attitude and their academic achievement in science education have direct relation. Students with positive attitude towards science education have high achievement and the affective practices of students in and out of the classroom are strongly related to their academic achievement. Students are effectively successful through practicing the subject matters. Students tend to understand and recall what they see more than what they hear as a result of using laboratories in the teaching and learning of science students so as to get better achievement.

The goal of secondary schools is to support high-quality learning while giving individual students the opportunity to choose programs that suit their skills and interests. An updated curriculum, in combination with a broader range of learning options outside traditional classroom instruction, will enable students to better customize their high school education and improve their prospects for success in school and in life.

Students have many responsibilities with regard to their learning, and these increase as they advance through secondary school. Students who are willing to make the effort required and who are able to monitor their thinking and learning strategies and apply themselves will soon discover that there is a direct relationship between this effort and their achievement, and will therefore be more motivated to work. Students who developmental attitudes and ways of behaving that contribute to success in life will benefit as learners. Successful mastery of scientific concepts and investigation skills requires students to have a

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sincere commitment to work and to the development of appropriate learning skills. Furthermore, students should actively pursue opportunities outside the classroom to extend and enrich their scientific understanding and skills.

The science curriculum has the potential to stimulate interest in lifelong learning not only for students but also for their parents and all those with an interest in education. In addition to supporting regular school activities, parents may want to take an active interest in current events and issues in the field of science, and to provide their children with opportunities to question and reflect on the impact of these developments on their immediate lives, the environment, and society. Parents can also provide valuable support by encouraging children to take part in activities that develop responsible citizenship or that further their interest in science.

According to Evangelista (2015), researchers, educators and educational policy makers show increasing concern on the need for greater emphasis on student-centered science instruction in response to the increasing issues on students' performance. Science teaching has become more flexible, responsive and dynamic to meet the changing times and to take into account the influences of the contemporary psychologists. As such, there has been a change in emphasis for science teaching.

The hows of teaching science is not only limited to discovery and process approaches. Other methods, such as the use of material sources or instructional aids supplement the major methods where children learn both content and processes of science. Furthermore, Oladejo and Isola (2011) claimed that the place of instructional materials in the effective implementation of any education program cannot be undermined. Instructional materials perform such functions as the extension of the range of experience available to learners, supplement and complement the teacher's verbal explanations thereby making learning experience richer and providing the teacher with interest into a wide variety of learning activities.

Teachers are responsible for developing appropriate instructional strategies to help students achieve the curriculum expectations, as well as appropriate methods for assessing and evaluating student learning. Teachers bring enthusiasm and varied teaching and assessment approaches to the classroom, addressing individual students' needs and ensuring sound learning opportunities for every student.

Using a variety of instructional, assessment, and evaluation strategies, teachers provide numerous hands-on opportunities for students to develop and refine their investigation skills, including their problem-solving skills, critical and creative thinking skills, and communication skills, while discovering fundamental concepts through inquiry, exploration, observation, and research. The activities offered should enable students to relate and apply these concepts to the social, environmental, and economic conditions and concerns of the world in which they live. Opportunities to relate knowledge and skills to these wider contexts will motivate students to learn in a meaningful way and to become lifelong learners.

Teachers need to help students understand that problem solving of any kind often requires a considerable expenditure of time and energy and a good deal of perseverance. Teachers also need to encourage students to investigate, to reason, to explore alternative solutions, and to take the risks necessary to become successful problem solvers.

Science can play a key role in shaping students' views about life and learning. Science exists in a broader social and economic context. It is affected by the values and choices of individuals, businesses, and governments and, in turn, has a significant impact on society and the environment.

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There is a consensus that in many places around the world, science education is facing serious challenges. Those seeking to improve science education face numerous, and sometimes coupled, problems. In many places, the lack of resources – both educational and financial – is linked with a dearth of adequately trained teachers and the growing popularity of non-scientifically-based belief systems. As countries face the demands of expanding populations under economic constraints and political realities, education as a whole is frequently one of the first areas in which funding is cut to free up resources for other, apparently more pressing, demands.

This trend is amplified in the area of sciences, since often those in the political decision-making sector have limited appreciation of scientific disciplines and their importance to the vitality of their country's economy and future well-being. It is clear that developing countries face greater challenges in science education than economically developed countries due to lack of teaching materials, including books, computer and communications technologies, community-based science centers, laboratory facilities and equipment, as well as shortage of skilled teachers.

In order to attain or reach globally competitive learners and produce a 21st century learner, science has been the keystone to quality education. Science is an active subject that demands that hands-on and mind-on experiences that challenge pupils' initiatives are encouraged. Teaching methods that promote understanding and thinking with emphasis on scientific processes should be employed and the rote learning of scientific facts de-emphasized. Also, there is a need for science teachers to take the abstract notion out of science by using real-to-life, simple and down-to-earth instructional materials which can be resourced from the environment.

Resources for science teaching are not only found in the classroom, but they are also available in the immediate school environment and community. As such, a science teacher should be familiar with the immediate school environment and the community in order to be able to source out all the human and non-human materials that can facilitate science learning.

In the Philippines, the study of science is mandatory in all levels of education and the state is mandated to give priority to science and technology education, training and services. Educators viewed that science education is one of the essential tools to national development and suggested that there must be a strong commitment from the academe to attain this goal.

In line with the aforementioned, this researcher decided to conduct the study and propose support instructional materials in Science using contextualized and localized activities to enhance the competency in Science of the Grade 9 learners of Galvan High School in Guimba West District, Division of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2020-2021.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on three science educational theories, namely: Skinner's behaviorism, Piaget's constructivism and Kolby's experiential learning theories as cited by Zhou and Brown (2018).

The behaviorist theory is the traditional approach to teaching Science. It ensures mastery of each step before going on to the next, using practice, examinations and many examples to do this. If mastery is not demonstrated, then we take them back to a previous step and work through it again which is a learning loop.

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A behaviorist approach to teaching and learning in Science is very boring for the learner. It's just a list of things that are hard to remember. You can make people remember things by repetition, practice and testing, but you cannot make them understand it. At best it is only surface level learning. The most important things we learn are those things we remember when all the facts have been forgotten.

Behaviorism, also called traditional learning theory holds that learning is what changes behavior and thus causes development. Behaviorists believe that human beings of all ages learn about the world in the same way that other animals do, by reacting to features of their environments that they find pleasing, painful or threatening. Behaviorism is the psychological school which holds that information about the mind can be reliably derived only from observation of behavior and not from reports of conscious experience.

Quality teaching should be aimed at promoting deep level processing of information in the mind of the learner. The developmentalist view sees learning as the process of developing a learner's personal schema towards a more complex and sophisticated conceptual structure. That is concept mapping. Concept mapping might identify and develop networks of ideas on the mind of students. That is, concepts change teaching. Concepts change learning.

Jean Piaget through his clinical interviews, researched the position that knowledge is constructed in the mind of the learner. He believed that young children think differently in most circumstances, than do older children and adults. Thus, young children require a special kind of curriculum because their thinking is more concrete and less logical. For example, according to Piaget, children in the preoperational stage this book focus on one variable at a time, such as length or width, and are egocentric and animistic. That is, they believe that the world revolves around them, have trouble taking the point of view of another, and impute life to inanimate things. More recently, other theories have argued that the reason young children think differently is their very lack of experience with the world. The benchmarks and content standards do take a developmental view of science teaching, cautioning teachers, for example, not to reinforce young children's beliefs that animals have thoughts and feelings similar to their own.

Lev Vygotsky added significantly to Piaget's theories by postulating that the important factors in moving children to higher levels of thought are the significant and more accomplished others around them. Thus, if an adult believes that the child is very close to constructing a concept, he may act to ask a question, provide a tool, or suggest a course of action that will move the child forward. Good questions motivate children. When students are asked open-ended questions, they will pose innovative questions of their own, thus expanding their capacity for creative thinking and problem solving.

Another view on teaching and learning in Science is "The Constructivism". This view sees the teacher's job as assisting students to construct new meanings. There are three main principles of Constructivism.

1. The learning outcomes of any teaching depend not only upon the teaching you do, but also on the knowledge, purpose, motivations and beliefs that the learners bring with them to the classroom.
2. Learning is an active process in which the learner must be actively involved.
3. Learners have the final responsibility for their own learning. Responsibility for learning is the learner's, not the teacher's.

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To sum up, different theories are of equal importance and of equal use, but the major theoretical development is a greater awareness of, and a move towards, the constructivist perspective and view of how people learn science.

The third theory of learning is experiential learning. As the name suggests, experiential learning involves learning from experience. According to Kolb, this type of learning can be defined as "the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience. Knowledge results from the combinations of grasping and transforming experience."

Experiential learning theory differs from cognitive and behavioral theories in that cognitive theories emphasize the role of mental processes while behavioral theories ignore the possible role of subjective experience in the learning process. The experiential theory proposed by Kolb takes a more holistic approach and emphasizes how experiences, including cognitions, environmental factors, and emotions influence the learning process.

In the experiential model, Kolb described two different ways of grasping experience: Concrete Experience and Abstract Conceptualization. He also identified two ways of transforming experience: Reflective Observation and Active Experimentation. These four modes of learning are often portrayed as a cycle.

According to Kolb, concrete experience provides the information that serves as a basis for reflection. From these reflections, we assimilate the information and form abstract concepts. We then use these concepts to develop new theories about the world, which we then actively test. Through the testing of our ideas, we once again gather information through experience, cycling back to the beginning of the process. The process does not necessarily begin with experience, however. Instead, each person must choose which learning mode will work best based upon the specific situation.

Kolb suggests that a number of different factors can influence preferred learning styles. Some of the factors that he has identified include: Personality type, Educational specialization Career choice, Current job role, and Adaptive competencies.

Conceptual Framework

This study has as its legal bases the 1987 Philippine Constitution, Education Act of 1982 and Republic Act No. 10533 otherwise known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013.

Every Filipino citizen deserves to be educated. Aware of this, the State is tasked to provide equal educational opportunities to every individual. Explicitly, Section 1 of Article XIV of the 1987 Philippine Constitution states:

"The State shall protect and provide the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels, and shall take appropriate steps to make sure education accessible to all."

In the promotion of the individual's right to education, the State shall establish, maintain and support a complete, adequate and integrated system of education relevant to the needs of the people and society. It shall likewise establish and maintain a system of free public education in the elementary and high school levels. Without limiting the natural rights of parents to rear their children, elementary education is compulsory for all children of school age.

Rule II, Section I of the Education Act of 1982 defines the basic state policy and educational objectives as follows:

"It has been declared a basic state policy that the educational system make maximum contribution to the attainment of national development goals; that among others,

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the state promote and maintain equality of access to education and of enjoyment of the benefits of education by all citizens; that the state recognize education as an instrument for the development of the cultural communities of the nation; that the educational system reach out to serve educationally deprived communities to enrich their participation in the community and national life, and to unify all Filipinos into a free and just nation.”

It is therefore the duty of all officers and employees involved in the administration of the educational system, as provided for in the Act, and as embodied as principles in the Constitution, as well as relevant policies under existing laws.

Republic Act No. 10533 otherwise known as the “Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013” declared the policy of the State that every graduate of basic education shall be an empowered individual who has learned, through a program that is rooted on sound educational principles and geared towards excellence, the foundations for learning throughout life, the competence to engage in work and be productive, the ability to coexist in fruitful harmony with local and global communities, the capability to engage in autonomous, creative, and critical thinking, and the capacity and willingness to transform others and one’s self.

For this purpose, the State shall create a functional basic education system that will develop productive and responsible citizens equipped with the essential competencies, skills and values for both life-long learning and employment. In order to achieve this, the State shall:

- a. Give every student an opportunity to receive quality education that is globally competitive based on a pedagogically sound curriculum that is at par with international standards;
- b. Broaden the goals of high school education for college preparation, vocational and technical career opportunities as well as creative arts, sports and entrepreneurial employment in a rapidly changing and increasingly globalized environment; and
- c. Make education learner-oriented and responsive to the needs, cognitive and cultural capacity, the circumstances and diversity of learners, schools and communities through the appropriate languages of teaching and learning, including mother tongue as a learning resource.

Figure 1 presents the schematic diagram of the conceptual framework of the study through the Input-Process-Output model.

The inputs of the study include the academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students of Galvan High School for school year 2020-2021 and the least learned competencies in Science 9. Based on the analysis of their academic performance, support instructional materials were proposed to enhance the competency in Science of the Grade 9 students. The developed support instructional materials were evaluated by experts as to their acceptability.

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Figure 1
Schematic Diagram of the Conceptual Framework of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study sought to assess the academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students in Galvan High School, Guimba West District, Division of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2020-2021.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students?
2. What are the least learned competencies in Science 9?
3. What support instructional materials can be developed to enhance the competencies in Science of the Grade 9 students?
4. How acceptable are the proposed support instructional materials as evaluated by experts?
- 5.

Basic Assumptions

This study was anchored on the following basic assumptions:

1. The Grade 9 students had fairly satisfactory level of academic performance based on their final rating in Science for school year 2020-2021.

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2. The least learned competencies in Science 9 served as the basis for the development of support instructional materials.
3. The proposed support instructional materials can enhance the competence in Science of the Grade 9 students.
4. The proposed instructional materials are acceptable based on evaluation of experts.
- 5.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study was conducted in Galvan High School, Guimba West District, Nueva Ecija during the school year 2020-2021. It was delimited to the level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students.

The level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students was based on their final rating in Science for school year 2020-2021. The analysis of the least learned competencies in Science was the basis for developing support instructional materials to improve their academic performance. The least learned competencies were determined based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) which were ranked by the teacher-respondents based on the answers of the Grade 9 students in the self-learning modules (SLMs). The developed support learning materials were evaluated by experts as to their acceptability.

Significance of the Study

The results of the study will be beneficial to the following:

School Administrators. The results of the study can be used as a frame of reference for determining future programs in the teaching of Science.

Science Teachers. The results of the study will be useful as a reference and as inspiration for new teaching strategies and as affirmation of techniques already used in the classroom.

Grade 9 Students. They are the direct beneficiaries of this study for the results will give them more opportunities to improve their academic performance. The variety of learning resources, techniques and sources will create interesting and exciting lessons that are appealing and engaging for students. As a result, the students will receive the quality of education they deserve.

Researcher Herself. The results of this study will help her understand and be aware of the changes in the implementation of Science through the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). It can widen her horizons on the objectives of Science and at the same time improve her teaching capabilities relative to the teaching of the subject with the revisions made.

Future Researchers. They can undertake similar studies on a wider scope to validate the findings of the study.

Definition of Terms

For a better understanding of the study, the following terms are hereby operationally defined:

Academic Performance. In this study, this refers to the final rating in Science of the Grade 9 students for School Year 2020-2021 assessed as follows: Outstanding (90-100%); Very Satisfactory (85-89%); Satisfactory (80-84%); Fairly Satisfactory (75-79%); and Did Not Meet Expectations (Below 75%).

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Least Learned Competencies. As used in the study, these refer to the identified weaknesses in Science of the Grade 9 students. These are based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) and are based on the ranking of the teachers on the results of assessing the self-learning modules (SLMs).

Support Instructional Materials. These are outputs of the study developed as support instructional materials in the teaching of Science for Grade 9 students based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs).

CHAPTER 2 METHODOLOGY

This chapter describes the methods and procedures adapted in the conduct of the study which includes the research design, sources of data, instrumentation and data collection, and tools for data analysis.

Research Design

This study sought to assess the level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students in Galvan High School, Guimba West District, Nueva Ecija during the school year 2020-2021 through the quantitative-descriptive research design.

The quantitative-descriptive research design was utilized to determine the level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students based on their final rating for school year 2020-2021. It was also used to look into the least learned competencies in Science of the Grade 9 students. Based on the findings, support instructional materials were proposed to enhance the level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students. The developed support instructional materials were evaluated by experts as to their acceptability in terms of content, quality of presentation, and physical make-up.

Sources of Data

The sources of data in this study were the teachers of Science in Galvan High School, Guimba West District, Nueva Ecija who provided data needed to answer the sub-problems raised in the study.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

To gather the data needed in this study, the researcher used the final rating in Science of the Grade 9 students during the school year 2020-2021 to determine their level of academic performance. The Grade 9 students' least learned competencies in Science were also determined based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) in Science. These were ranked by the teacher respondents based on the answers of the students in the Self-Learning Modules (SLMs). Based on the data gathered, support instructional materials were proposed to enhance the level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students.

Tools for Data Analysis

Weighted Mean was utilized to treat the data statistically.

To answer sub-problem number 3, weighted mean (WM) was utilized.

The formula is:

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$$WM = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean

$\sum fx$ = the sum of the products per column

fx = the number of responses per column multiplied by the assigned weighted mean

N = the number of respondents

To interpret the data, the following reference was used:

Point Value	Statistical Limit	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Acceptable (HA)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Acceptable (VA)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Acceptable (MA)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Acceptable (SA)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Acceptable (NA)

CHAPTER 3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the data gathered and their analysis and interpretation to answer the sub-problems raised in the study.

Level of Academic Performance in Science of the Grade 9 Students

This section presents the level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students in Galvan High School, Guimba West Deistrict, Nueva Ecija during the school year 2020 – 2021 based on their final ratings to answer sub-problem number 1.

In Science, the final ratings of the Grade 9 students are shown as follows: Outstanding (95-100%); Above Average (90-94%); Average (85-89%); Fair (80-84%); Poor (80-84%); and Did Not Meet Expectation (Below 75%).

In line with this, Table 1 presents the academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students of Galvan High School.

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TABLE 1
Level of Academic Performance
in Science

Performance Rating	f	%
Outstanding (95-100%)	14	5.86
Above Average (90-94%)	24	10.04
Average (85-89%)	54	22.59
Fair (80-84%)	147	61.51
Poor (75-79%)	0	0
Did Not Meet Expectations (Below 75%)	0	0
TOTAL	239	100%

As presented in Table 1, of the 239 Grade 9 students in Science, 14 or 5.86% obtained outstanding level of performance or ratings of 95 – 100%. There were 24 students or 10.04% whose final ratings were 90-94% described as above average performance. This indicates a high degree of understanding of concepts and skills in Science. There were 54 students or 22.59% with 85-89% final rating described as average performance which indicates a good grasp of scientific concepts and skills. Most of the Grade 9 students had final ratings of 80-84% described as fair performance. These students (147 or 61.51%) had weak acquisition of skills and concepts in Science. No one had poor performance with 75-79% final ratings to indicate little understanding of scientific concepts and skills.

These results imply the need to develop support instructional materials in Science for the Grade 9 students to enhance their level of performance in the subject.

Least Learned of Competencies in Science

This section presents the least learned competencies in Science of the Grade 9 students of Galvan High School during the school year 2020 – 2021 to answer sub-problem number 2.

Table 2 presents the data.

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TABLE 2
Least Learned Competencies in Science

Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs)	RANK
• Explain how the respiratory and circulatory systems work	1
• Describe basic features and importance of photosynthesis	2
• Explain how the structure of the carbon atom affects the type of bonds it forms	3
• Use the mole concept to express mass of substance	4
• Explain what happens when volcanoes erupt	5
• Show which constellations may be observed at different times of the year	6
• Explain how ions are formed	7
• Describe the different types of volcanoes	8
• Recognize different types of compounds based on their properties	9
• Describe certain climate phenomena that occur on a global level	10

As presented in Table 2, the least learned competencies in Science of the Grade 9 students were determined based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). The teachers ranked the least learned competencies based on the answers of the Grade 9 students in the Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) in Science. Rank number 1 is explaining how the respiratory and circulatory systems work, followed by describing basic features and importance of photosynthesis. Rank number 10 is describing certain climate phenomena that occur on a global level.

The K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum is standards-based. The content standards cover a specified scope of topics which sets the essential knowledge and understanding that must be learned. The performance standards describe the abilities and skills that the learners are expected to demonstrate in relation to the content standards. These standards are further represented as learning competencies which are the knowledge, skills and attitudes that students need to demonstrate in every lesson or learning activity.

The Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) maintain core learning objectives in Science. In defining MELCs, the standard of enduring lifelong learning was used – knowledge that remains for a long time that learners can use in their lives.

Proposed Support Instructional Materials in Science

Support instructional materials were proposed to enhance the level of academic performance in Science of Grade 9 students in Galvan High School to answer sub-problem number 3. The proposed support instructional materials were based on the least learned competencies in Science of the Grade 9 students determined from the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) ranked by the teachers based on the answers of the students in the Self-Learning Modules (SLMs).

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Acceptability of the Support Instructional Materials in Science

This section is concerned with the acceptability of the proposed support instructional materials in Science for Grade 9 students based on the criteria adopted from Espinar (2017). The evaluation was based on content, quality of presentation and physical make-up.

Table 3 presents the data.

TABLE 3
Evaluation of Experts of the Developed Support Instructional Materials

CRITERIA	WM	DE
A. Content		
1. The terms and content are suitable to the level of Grade 9 students.	4.52	VA
2. The exercises are arranged in the order familiar to Grade 9 students.	4.50	VA
3. The instructions are clear and easy to follow.	4.55	VA
4. The concepts are within the Grade 9 students' level of experience.	4.54	VA
5. The number of exercises is limited so as not to overload or confuse the learners.	4.55	VA
Average WM	4.53	VA
B. Quality of Presentation		
1. The illustrations are clear and interesting.	4.51	VA
2. The lay-out of the materials can elicit learner's attention.	4.55	VA
3. The materials are simple and possess imaginative quality.	4.50	VA
Average WM	4.52	VA
C. Physical Make-up		
1. The instructional design of individual tasks is carefully planned.	4.55	VA
2. The size of the type and print is proper for the age level of Grade 9.	4.51	VA
3. The lay-out of the pages is appropriate for Grade 9 students.	4.50	VA
Average WM	4.52	VA
Overall Average WM	4.52	VA
Legend: WM = weighted mean		
Relative Values	Statistical Limit	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Acceptable (HA)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Acceptable (VA)

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3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Acceptable (MA)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Acceptable (SA)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Acceptable (NA)

The results of the perceptions of the Grade 9 students show that in terms of content, the proposed support instructional materials are “very acceptable” as evidenced by the average weighted mean that ranged from 4.50 – 4.55. The average weighted mean was 4.53 described as very acceptable. These have something to do with the suitability of the terms and content to the level of Grade 9 students, the familiarity of the Grade 9 students on the arrangement of the exercises, the clarity of the instructions being easy to follow, the concepts within the Grade 9 students' level of experience, and limitation of the number of exercises so as not to overload or confuse the learners. The results imply that the proposed support instructional materials can cater to the needs of the Grade 9 students in terms of content.

On the quality of the presentation, the illustrations are clear and interesting, the layout of the materials can elicit learner's attention, and materials are simple and possess imaginative quality with weighted means of 4.51, 4.55 and 4.50, respectively, all being “very acceptable.” These resulted in average weighted mean of 4.52 described as “very acceptable.”

As to physical make-up, the average weighted mean was 4.52 for a descriptive equivalent of “very acceptable.” This includes careful planning of the instructional design of individual tasks, proper size of the type and print for the age level of Grade 9 students and combined attractiveness with utility of the layout of the pages with weighted means of 4.55, 4.51 and 4.50, respectively.

Overall, the average weighted mean is 4.52 which means that the proposed support instructional materials are “very acceptable” as perceived by the experts.

Based on the results, the developed support instructional materials are accepted by the Science teachers. This implies that the materials could be used as a tool in enhancing the Grade 9 students' performance in Science.

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CHAPTER 4 SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of the study, the conclusions drawn based on the findings and the recommendations offered.

SUMMARY

This study sought to assess the level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students in Galvan High School, Guimba West District, Nueva Ecija during the school year 2020-2021 through the quantitative-descriptive research design.

The quantitative-descriptive research design was utilized to determine the level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students based on their final rating for school year 2020-2021. It was also used to look into the least learned competencies in Science of the Grade 9 students. Based on the findings, support instructional materials were proposed to enhance the level of academic performance in Science of the Grade 9 students. The developed support instructional materials were evaluated by experts as to their acceptability in terms of content, quality of presentation, and physical make-up.

The sources of data in this study were the teachers of Science in Galvan High School, Guimba West District, Nueva Ecija who provided data needed to answer the sub-problems raised in the study.

Summary of Findings:

1.0 Level of Academic Performance in Science of the Grade 9 Students

- 1.1 There were 14 Grade 9 students or 5.86% who obtained final ratings in Science of 95-100% described as "outstanding" performance.
- 1.2 There were 24 Grade 9 students or 10.04% who obtained final ratings in Science of 90-94% described as "above average" performance.
- 1.3 Fifty four Grade 9 students or 22.59% obtained final ratings in Science of 85-89% described as "average" performance.
- 1.4 There were 147 Grade 9 students or 61.51% who obtained final ratings in Science of 80-84% described as "fair" performance.

2.0 Least Learned Competencies in Science

The least learned competencies in Science of the Grade 9 students determined based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) are the following:

- 2.1 Explain how the respiratory and circulatory systems work;
- 2.2 Describe basic features and importance of photosynthesis;
- 2.3 Explain how the structure of the carbon atom affects the type of bonds it forms;
- 2.4 Use the mole concept to express mass of substance;
- 2.5 Explain what happens when volcanoes erupt;
- 2.6 Show which constellations may be observed at different times of the year;

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- 2.7 Explain how ions are formed;
- 2.8 Describe the different types of volcanoes;
- 2.9 Recognize different types of compounds based on their properties; and
- 2.10 Describe certain climate phenomena that occur on a global level.

3.0 Support Instructional Materials in Science

Support instructional materials in Science for Grade 9 students were proposed to enhance their level of academic performance.

4.0 Acceptability of the Support Instructional Materials in Science

- 5.1 In terms of content, the support instructional materials are “very acceptable” with average WM of 4.53, with all items as “very acceptable” also with WM of 4.52, 4.50, 4.55, 4.54, and 4.55.
- 5.2 In terms of quality of presentation, the materials were rated “very acceptable” with average WM of 4.52, with all items as “very acceptable” with WM of 4.51, 4.55 and 4.50.
- 5.3 In terms of physical make-up, the materials were “very acceptable” with average WM of 4.52, with all items also rated “very acceptable” with WM of 4.55, 4.51, and 4.50.
- 5.4 The support instructional materials were “very acceptable” with overall WM of 4.52.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Most of the Grade 9 students have fair level of academic performance in Science which indicates weak acquisition of skills and concepts in Science.
2. The least learned competencies in Science of the Grade 9 students are explaining how the respiratory and circulatory systems work, describing basic features and importance of photosynthesis, and explaining how the structure of the carbon atom affects the type of bonds it forms.
3. Support instructional materials in Science were proposed for the Grade 9 students to enhance their level of academic performance.
4. The proposed support instructional materials in Science are very acceptable based on the evaluation of experts.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were offered:

1. The proposed support instructional materials should be considered for use by school authorities concerned to enhance the level of academic performance of Grade 9 students.

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2. The developed support instructional materials should be tried out on a bigger scale for further improvement of the materials.
3. Teachers should be encouraged to develop instructional materials particularly on subject/ topics where most students encounter difficulties.
4. The school administration should provide support in the production of instructional materials developed by teachers.
5. Other researchers may conduct similar studies on a wider scope to validate the findings of the study.

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